

NAVIGATION PROBLEMS OF UAV AND THEIR SOLUTIONS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract:

With their cheap operating costs, simple deployment, and increased mobility, unmanned aerial vehicles, or UAVs, are finding increasing use in a range of applications. However, employing unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) at a distance and in complex environments restricts their capabilities and lowers the overall effectiveness of the system. As such, a large number of researchers are focused on autonomous UAV navigation, which allows UAVs to move and execute specific tasks based on their environment. The applications of artificial intelligence (AI) have increased as a result of recent technological advancements. Several AI techniques for autonomous UAV navigation have been thoroughly examined and categorized. The foundations, tenets, and salient characteristics of various optimization and learning-based techniques are reviewed in this study.

Keywords: Unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), artificial intelligence (AI), optimization, navigation, ant colony optimization (ACO), particle swarm optimization (PSO)

INTRODUCTION

Optimization-based techniques cover the traditional mathematically based AI problem-solving techniques. Any given non-deterministic polynomial-time hard (NP-hard) problem can be almost optimally solved with these algorithms. Despite this, these algorithms are extremely complex in terms of both time and space. This section provides a brief overview of the most widely used optimization-based AI techniques for autonomous UAV navigation. The PSO and ACO algorithm. A comparative analysis of these optimization-based AI systems is also shown in Table 1, with a focus on their salient features, temporal complexities with multiple m procedures, and hyper-parameter counts.

Table 1 Comparative study of different optimization based AI approaches

Algorithm	Type	Feature	Complexity	Hyper-parameter Count
PSO	MPSO	Covert the infeasible paths generated by PSO into feasible paths using an error factor	$O(mn^2)$	6
	DPSO	Takes discrete steps to propagate and multiple augmentations are done for better convergence	$O(mn+mn^2)$	5
	GBPSO	Compares the current global path with the other global path candidates to select the optimal one	$O(2mn^3+mn^2)$	7
ACO	Multi-Aco	Solves the TSP problem and both intra-colony and inter-colony pheromone values are considered	$O(mn^2)$	8
	Double-ACO	Utilizes GA to generate the initial population	$O(mn^2)$	9
	PFAO	Utilizes MMAS and APF for better global searching, fast convergence	$O(mn^2)$	4

PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION (PSO)

PSO was first introduced by Eberhart and Kennedy in 1995. PSO is a population-based search technique meant to resemble a variety of animal species, such as birds and bees. Each animal in PSO can be represented as a three-dimensional vector particle. PSO uses a particle's velocity and current position to calculate its motion. The particle's velocity continuously updates based on its own optimal position vector (P_{best}) and the swarm's (G_{best}), as shown in Fig. 1. PSO is in its ideal position when it achieves its goal or the least amount of error possible.

Figure 1. Particle swarm optimization (PSO)

PSO manages the movement of UAVs in a three-dimensional space by treating them like particles during UAV navigation. Autor Jalal altered the traditional PSO in [1] to enable offline UAV navigation around obstructions. Similar to a traditional PSO, the modified PSO (MPSO) models an extra error element to guarantee convergence. The error factor's primary job is to change the unfeasible paths produced by PSO into workable ones. For verified optimality, MPSO moves and re-initializes particles that are inside an obstacle boundary. The authors simulated scenarios with both single and multiple obstacles to guarantee the effectiveness of the MPSO. Similar to this, Phung et al. changed the traditional continuous PSO into discrete PSO (DPSO) in order to address the issue of UAV path planning in [2]. The authors took discrete 3D space and obstacles into consideration when modeling the UAV path planning problem as a traveling salesman problem (TSP). In addition, the DPSO's convergence was accelerated by using random mutation, edge exchange, deterministic initialization, and parallel GPU implementation techniques. A competition strategy-based PSO (GBPSO) was presented by Huang et al. in 2018 [3] to choose the global optimal path for UAVs. To determine the best path for particles, the suggested competition technique contrasts the existing global path with other global path possibilities.

ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION (ACO)

As the name suggests, ants' method of food gathering served as inspiration for ACO. Ants use a highly volatile chemical called pheromone to communicate and cooperate while looking for food. Ants emit pheromones as they search for routes to a food source and start looking for it initially. The first ant's pheromone trails are followed by other ants, who take different paths to the food supply. The ant colony that finds the shortest path will therefore have a higher concentration of pheromones, as Figure 2 illustrates. Moreover, the concentration of pheromones on the abandoned routes declines with time.

Figure 2. Ant colony optimization (ACO)

Cekmez et al. developed a multi-colony ACO-based method in [4] for

autonomous UAV navigation while avoiding obstacles in a 3D space. The authors claim that the premature convergence issue brought on by single-colony ACO is resolved by multi-colony ACO. The UAV navigation problem was first stated by the authors as a TSP problem, after which several UAV groups looked for the best routes to the target. The UAVs are in charge of both intra- and inter-colony pheromone value exchange in multi-colony ACO. Similar to this, Guan et al. presented a double-colony ACO in [5] where pheromones are produced by taking use of the GA.

To solve the premature convergence issue, it is suggested combining an artificial potential field (APF) with an ACO called potential field ACO (PFAO). The APF algorithm is designed to avoid obstacles and maintain the UAV's optimal speed and safety in environments where there are repulsive and gravitational forces. Moreover, to enhance global searching, the APF modifies a UAV's transition probability from one ACO node to another. Additionally, the authors updated the global pheromone value for faster convergence while identifying the best and worst paths using the min-max ant system (MMAS) and weakening the worst path.

CONCLUSION

In complicated and dynamic environments, autonomous UAV navigation has improved performance and brought about significant flexibility. To introduce the reader to UAV architecture, this survey focuses on the key traits and varieties of UAVs. In addition, an overview of the application-based classification and UAV navigation system was provided to facilitate researchers' understanding of the ideas presented in this survey. The foundations, guiding principles, and essential elements of several AI algorithms used by various researchers for autonomous UAV navigation were explained in terms of optimization-based and learning-based techniques. Various optimization-based techniques, including the PSO and ACO algorithms, were examined and emphasized.

References:

1. L. Dlwari, "Three-dimensional off-line path planning for unmanned aerial vehicle using modified particle swarm optimization," *International Journal of Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering*, vol. 9, no. 8, pp. 1–5, Jan. 2015.
2. M. D. Phung, C. H. Quach, Q. Ha, and T. H. Dinh, "Enhanced discrete particle swarm optimization path planning for UAV vision-based surface inspection," *Autom. Construct.*, vol. 81, pp. 25–33, Sep. 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0926580517303825>

3. C. Huang and J. Fei, "UAV path planning based on particle swarm optimization with global best path competition," *Int. J. Pattern Recognit. Artif. Intell.*, vol. 32, no. 6, Jun. 2018, Art. no. 1859008.
4. U. Cekmez, M. Ozsiginan, and O. K. Sahingoz, "Multi colony ant optimization for UAV path planning with obstacle avoidance," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Unmanned Aircr. Syst. (ICUAS)*, Jun. 2016, pp. 47–52.
5. Y. Guan, M. Gao, and Y. Bai, "Double-ant colony based UAV path planning algorithm," in *Proc. 11th Int. Conf. Mach. Learn. Comput.*, 2019, pp. 258–262, doi: 10.1145/3318299.3318376.

